

NOVEL ELLIPTIC CURVE SCALAR MULTIPLICATION ALGORITHMS FOR FASTER AND SAFER PUBLIC-KEY CRYPTOSYSTEMS

Vinay S. Iyengar

Oregon Episcopal School, Portland, Oregon, USA
iyengarvi@go.oes.edu

ABSTRACT

Efficient and secure public-key cryptosystems are essential in today's age of rapidly growing Internet communications. Elliptic curve scalar multiplication in particular, which refers to the operation of multiplying a large integer by a point on an elliptic curve, is crucial for both data encryption technology as well as testing the security of cryptographic systems. The purpose of this project was to design and implement an elliptic curve scalar multiplication algorithm 10% faster than one of the best algorithms currently used: the binary double-add algorithm. The algorithm designed was based off of an operation that allowed for the tripling of a point and was derived from point doubling and addition operations. The algorithm was further optimized using an integer representation in both ternary and balanced ternary form. Finally, a novel modification was made that allowed for the pre-computation and storage of multiples of a point. The algorithms were written and tested in a C++ program that selected random points over elliptic curves in both Weierstrass and Edwards form, and multiplied them by a large range of integers using each of the various algorithms. Timings for these operations were taken in terms of processor cycles and finally averaged out. The final averaged results showed that the most optimized algorithm was 66.63% more efficient than the binary double-add algorithm. In conclusion, the algorithm designed in this research showed a large improvement in efficiency compared to one of the best algorithms in commercial use today, and has significant implications for the field of cryptography.

KEYWORDS

Public-key cryptography, elliptic curves, scalar multiplication, point tripling, storage ladder.

1. INTRODUCTION

The term cryptography refers to the design and analysis of mathematical techniques that enable secure communication in the presence of malicious adversaries [4]. Public-key cryptography in particular refers to the cryptographic system where two keys are used, a public key and a private key. One is used to encrypt plaintext and the other used to decrypt cipher text, where neither key can be used for both functions [3]. This process is displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Public-key encryption/decryption process [12]

Public-key (PK) encryption systems are used nowadays to encrypt sensitive information like credit card numbers and passwords over an Internet protocol because the two communicating parties, for example a smartphone user and a bank server, must communicate without having previously decided on a secret key. These systems are also widely used by government agencies in order to maintain confidentiality in their communications, and in particular to conduct key exchange algorithms so the two communicating parties can decide on a shared secret key for symmetric-key encryption [3]. Given the large increase in people using the Internet for banking and transactions, efficient and secure public-key encryption algorithms are a necessity. As the power of computing increases, the algorithms for hacking cryptographic systems are also becoming more and more sophisticated, which is another reason why research must be done in improving the performance of PK encryption algorithms.

One of the most popular public-key cryptosystem in commercial use today is known as the RSA system. It is based off of the difficulty of finding the value of prime numbers P and Q given their product PQ . In 1985, Neal Koblitz and Victor Miller independently proposed using elliptic curves to design public-key cryptographic systems as an alternate to the RSA system [6]. Elliptic curves are a type of cubic equation of the form $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$, where a and b represent integer coefficients. This form of elliptic curves is known as the Weierstrass equation and is the most standard form of elliptic curves used in number theory [5]. Elliptic curve cryptosystems (ECC) are based on the Abelian group formed by elliptic curves over a finite field. This essentially means that operations can be done on points on the curve such as addition of two points, where the result is a third point on the curve, as shown in Figure 2 below [4].

Figure 2. Geometric Representation of Weierstrass Addition [13] and Graphical Representation of Multiple Edwards Curves [14]

Given this property, it is possible to design cryptographic algorithms based on difficult number-theoretic problems within this group [10]. For ECC this difficult problem is the Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem (ECDLP), which states that it is difficult to find a point P and integer k , given their product $P*k$. Another form of elliptic curves that will be studied in this project is the Edwards equation of the form $x^2 + y^2 = 1 + dx^2y^2$, where d represents an integer coefficient. Both of these forms of elliptic curves are used for cryptographic applications because each has specific characteristics that are more attractive to specific cryptographic algorithms. Weierstrass curves are an industry standard and are one of the fastest, but Edwards curves are also very efficient and have a unified group operation, meaning the same formula for point addition and doubling. This makes them resistant to side-channel attacks such as power or timing analysis, because the double and addition are difficult to tell apart [7]. Both forms though operate in the exact same fundamental manner, the only difference being they have different equations and different formulas for operations such as point addition and doubling [1]. In the late 1990's, ECC started gaining wide commercial acceptance and since then has become a popular alternative to the RSA algorithm, because of ECC's high security and efficiency. For example, the best-known algorithm for breaking the RSA cryptosystem has a sub-exponential running time versus an exponential running time to break the ECDLP. Thus, it is widely accepted that ECC offers equivalent level security for key-sizes that are almost 6 times smaller [4]. This translates into faster more secure public-key encryption as well as less storage, bandwidth, and power consumption. As of 2005, the National Security Agency (NSA) has added ECC to its set of standard cryptographic algorithms.

One of the most important operations for all applications of elliptic curves is scalar multiplication. This term refers to the operation of multiplying an integer by a point on an elliptic curve. Often the integer multiplied by the point is very large, so being able to do this efficiently is very important. EC scalar multiplication does not work like normal multiplication and is a far more complex process that is made up of a series of smaller operations. More specifically, over elliptic curves, operations exist only for doubling a point and for adding two points together. Thus, scalar multiplication consists of computing the value of a large integer multiplied by a point by doing a series of point doublings and additions until the product point is reached. One of the best algorithms currently used commercially is known as the "Binary Double-Add algorithm" and is also referred to as "binary exponentiation". This algorithm works by taking the integer and converting it into binary form. The algorithm then traverses through the binary form of the integer and decides to do a double or add based on whether the value of the bit is a '1' or '0' [4]. Elliptic curve scalar multiplication has applications towards both elliptic curve cryptosystems (ECC) as well testing the security of RSA methods using the Lenstra elliptic curve factorization method [8].

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION

The purpose of this project is to design and implement an elliptic curve scalar multiplication algorithm 10% faster than the Binary Double-Add algorithm. It is hypothesized that by deriving an operation for point tripling and by creating an algorithm from this operation, a more efficient scalar multiplication algorithm will be created. Both the Binary Double-Add algorithm as well as the novel algorithms created in this project will be written in a C++ program. They will be tested by using them to multiply points by a large range of random integers and computing the time to do those operations in terms of processor cycles. These algorithms will be tested over both Weierstrass and Edwards curves because both are commonly used in real life cryptographic algorithms. The timings for each algorithm will be averaged out and compared to the Binary Double-Add algorithm to see if they meet the goal of a 10% increase in speed. If a more efficient EC scalar multiplication algorithm can be created, it can have major implications for Internet communications.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

The main instrument used in this project was a Windows 7 Personal Computer with an Intel Core i5 processor installed with a Microsoft Visual Studio compiler. The main program was written in C++, and other tools such as Notepad and Microsoft excel were used to transfer and analyse the data.

An open source program with basic elliptic curve implementation from The Code Project website was used as the starting point for the project. This program had a very basic structure of the Weierstrass form of elliptic curves over a finite field. The next part of the research involved creating a new program based of the Weierstrass program that implemented the Edwards form of elliptic curves. This was done by first changing the program to generate points over the equation of Edwards curves shown in the introduction. Then, new equations for point addition and doubling a point were implemented. At this point, the basic apparatus for testing was complete, and the focus became the design and implementation of various scalar multiplication algorithms.

The first algorithm implemented was the commercially well-known Binary Double-Add (BDA) algorithm, which served as the standard to which all others were compared. This algorithm as well as all others tested, was implemented into both programs for Weierstrass and Edwards curves. The rest of the project involved engineering new algorithms in the attempt to create an algorithm faster than the BDA algorithm.

Algorithm 1: Binary Double-Add

INPUT: $k = (k_{t-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_2$, Point P

OUTPUT: $k * P$

1. Point $Q = \infty$
 2. For i from 0 to $t-1$ do
 - a. If $k_i = 1$ then $Q \leftarrow Q + P$
 - b. $P \leftarrow 2P$
 3. Return Q
-

The Binary Double-Add algorithm computes the value of an integer k by a point P by first looking at the binary representation of the integer. Then, depending on whether each bit is a 0 or 1, the algorithm does a double only or a double and an add.

The second algorithm implemented was a triple-double-add algorithm that used a function of tripling a point, which was derived from the formulas of doubling and addition.

Algorithm 2: Triple-Double-Add Draft 1

INPUT: k , Point P

OUTPUT: $k * P$

1. Point $Q = P$, $x = 1$
 2. While $3x < k$ do
 - a. $Q \leftarrow 3 * Q$
 - b. $x \leftarrow 3 * x$
 3. Call Algorithm 1 for input P, $k-x$
 4. Return result of Algorithm 1 + Q
-

This algorithm works by doing repeated tripling of a point, following by doubling, and then single additions in the manner of the Binary Double-Add algorithm. It was tested against the first by seeing how many processor cycles it took each algorithm to do various scalar multiplications of random numbers multiplied by a point. After these numbers were collected, an average of the speeds was taken as an indication of the overall efficiency of the algorithm.

The next optimization made was the implementation of a Ternary Expansion algorithm.

Algorithm 3: Ternary Expansion

INPUT: $k = (k_{t-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_3$, Point P

OUTPUT: $k * P$

1. Point $Q = \infty$
 2. For i from 0 to t-1 do
 - a. If $k_i = 1$ then $Q \leftarrow Q + P$
 - b. If $k_i = 2$ then $Q \leftarrow Q + 2P$
 - c. $P \leftarrow 3P$
 3. Return Q
-

This algorithm transforms the value of the integer into base 3, also known as ternary form. Then, the instruction to do a triple, double or add is given based on the value of each bit of the ternary representation. A '2' corresponds to a double and triple, a '1' to an add and triple, and a '0' to just a triple. This algorithm was tested in the exact same manner as the test above, and then further improved with a balanced ternary expansion.

Algorithm 4: Balanced Ternary Expansion

INPUT: $k = (k_{t-1}, \dots, k_1, k_0)_3$, Point P

OUTPUT: $k * P$

1. Point $Q = \infty$
 2. For i from 0 to t-1 do
 - a. If $k_i = 1$ then $Q \leftarrow Q + P$
 - b. If $k_i = -1$ then $Q \leftarrow Q - P$
 - c. $P \leftarrow 3P$
 3. Return Q
-

Instead of representing the integer in ternary form, algorithm 4 represents it in balanced ternary form, which represents the integers in terms of '1', '0' and '-1' rather than '0', '1' and '2'. A '1' is an add and triple, a '-1' a subtract and triple, and a '0' is just a triple. In order to implement this algorithm, a formula for point subtraction had to be derived from the formula for addition of an inverse.

The final optimization was then made on the best algorithms of each curve.

Algorithm 5: Storage Ladder

INPUT: Point P

OUTPUT: Array of first 32 multiplies of P either by 3 or 2

1. For i from 0-32 do
 - a. $Q \leftarrow P$
 - b. Store Q
 - c. $P \leftarrow 3 * P$ or $P \leftarrow 2 * P$
 2. Return table of 32 computed values
-

This optimization was the implementation of a novel storage ladder algorithm that pre-computed all the multiples of a point and then stored them. For example, the storage ladder optimization to a triple based algorithm pre-computed and stored $P, 3P, 9P, \dots, 3^{32}P$. The algorithms then worked the same way, but instead of re-computing the values, they called on the table from algorithm 5.

3.1 VALIDATION

In order to verify the method, each test was run multiple times to ensure that the numbers did not change drastically from test to test. The method was also verified by using the scalar multiplication algorithms in a real-life implementation of a Diffie-Hellman key exchange encryption algorithm. If a test vector was properly encrypted and decrypted, then the scalar multiplication algorithms worked correctly. After all the data was collected, it was analysed to test the effect of the size of an integer, on the efficiency of the scalar multiplication algorithm.

4. RESULTS

The following section is the visual model of the results of this research project, followed by a short paragraph noting specific data.

Figure 3. Comparison of Average Speeds: Weierstrass

The number of processor cycles was calculated for 117 integers randomly chosen within a range of $4 * 10^6$ to $(2^{32} - 1)$ and averaged for each algorithm. Figure 3 shows the average and standard deviation for the 5 algorithms tested over Weierstrass curves. The Binary Double-Add algorithm with storage ladder is the fastest algorithm over Weierstrass curves with an average of 24.44 ± 4.55 processor cycles compared to an average of 69.77 ± 5.19 processor cycles for the Binary Double-Add algorithm. All algorithms show a low standard deviation relative to their overall speed. The key inference is that all algorithms were relatively stable, with respect to the magnitude of the integer.

Figure 4. Comparison of Average Speeds: Edwards

The number of processor cycles was again calculated for the 117 integers as the Weierstrass tests and averaged for each algorithm. Figure 4 shows the average and standard deviation for the 5 algorithms tested over Edwards curves. The Balanced Ternary algorithm with storage ladder is the fastest algorithm over Edwards curves with an average of 35.86 ± 5.33 processor cycles compared to an average of 110.92 ± 8.78 processor cycles for the Binary Double-Add algorithm. All algorithms show a low standard deviation relative to their overall speed. The key inference is that all algorithms were relatively stable, with respect to the magnitude of the integer.

Figure 5. Integer Size vs. Algorithm Efficiency: Weierstrass

The value of the integer was plotted against the number of processor cycles it took to do the operation of that integer multiplied by a point over Weierstrass curves Figure 5 shows again that the Binary Double-Add storage ladder algorithm is the most efficient on Weierstrass curves. It also shows that the trend line of the algorithm has the lowest slope of all the algorithms at $1 * 10^{-10}$ compared to a slope of $2 * 10^{-9}$ for the Binary Double-Add algorithm. Based on the linearity of the trend line, it is clear that all algorithms have a computational complexity of $O(n)$.

Figure 6. Integer Size vs. Algorithm Efficiency: Edwards

The value of the integer was plotted against the number of processor cycles it took to do the operation of that integer multiplied by a point over Edwards curves. Figure 6 shows again that the Balanced Ternary algorithm with ladder algorithm is the most efficient on Edwards curves. It also shows that the trend line of the algorithm has the lowest slope of all the algorithms at approximately $7 * 10^{-10}$ compared to a slope of approximately $3 * 10^{-9}$ for the Binary Double-Add algorithm. Based on the linearity of the trend line, it is clear that all algorithms have a computational complexity of $O(n)$.

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The purpose of this research was to design and implement an elliptic curve scalar multiplication algorithm 10% faster than the Binary Double-Add (BDA) algorithm. It was hypothesized that creating a tripling-based algorithm would result in an increase in speed compared to the conventional doubling-based algorithm. The most optimized algorithm created on Weierstrass curves was 65.0% more efficient than the BDA algorithm, and the most optimized algorithm on Edwards curves was 67.7% more efficient than the BDA. Thus the goal of a 10% increase was not only met but also exceeded by an average of around 66%.

5.1 PERFORMANCE RESULTS

As shown in Figures 3 and 4, the Triple-Double-Add Draft 1 algorithm on Weierstrass and Edwards curves was 65.2% and 36.7% slower respectively than the BDA algorithm. The ternary integer representation though turned out to increase the speed to being 23.4% slower than the BDA on Weierstrass but 7.8% faster than the BDA on Edwards. The next stage of the algorithm with a representation in balanced ternary form increased the speed to being 15.1% slower than the BDA on Weierstrass and 18.3% faster than the BDA on Edwards by replacing each doubling operation with a subtraction operation. At this point, the fastest algorithm on Weierstrass curves was still the BDA algorithm, but the fastest on Edwards curves was the Balanced Ternary Expansion. Thus at this point, the research goal was met only on Edwards curves. This was due to the fact that the operation for tripling over Weierstrass curves was less efficient than the tripling operation derived for Edwards curves. The final optimization was a novel storage ladder implementation that pre-computed multiples of a point. This optimization was made to the best algorithm on each curve, so the BDA algorithm on Weierstrass curves and the Balanced Ternary

Expansion algorithm on Edwards curves. This algorithm had the largest increase in efficiency as is evident in figures 2 and 3, because each point operation was replaced by simply looking up the value in a table of pre-computed values. This was a large speed up and was a very efficient use of storage to increase efficiency. More specifically, simply the storage of 32 points, each of 2 32-bit integers, or 256 bytes of total storage resulted in around a 66% increase in speed.

5.2 ALGORITHM STABILITY

Figures 5 and 6 charted the value of the integer multiplied by a point versus the number of processor cycles. Finally a linear best-fit line was given to these plots. Based on this data, it is again evident that the fastest and most optimized algorithms on Weierstrass and Edwards are the best in terms of their slopes as well. A lower slope for the most optimized algorithms means that if larger numbers are used for scalar multiplication, these algorithms will be more efficient stable compared to the BDA algorithms. The optimized BDA algorithm on Weierstrass has a slope of approximately $1 * 10^{-9}$ compared to a slope of approximately $2 * 10^{-9}$ for the regular BDA algorithm. On Edwards, the Balanced Ternary storage ladder algorithm has a very efficient slope of $7 * 10^{-10}$ compared to a slope of $2 * 10^{-9}$ again for the regular BDA algorithm. This is a very important characteristic for elliptic curve scalar multiplication algorithms because it shows stability, and is another indication that the most optimized algorithms created in this project are better than the current standard algorithms.

5.3 OUTLIERS AND LIMITATIONS

For the most part, there are no outliers in the data. Some of the points on the graph of the Triple-Double-Add draft 1 algorithm shown in figures 4 and 5 show some variation in the points. This is due to the fact that this algorithm is quite inconsistent depending on the value of k. More specifically, it is more efficient for integers of the form $3x + 2y$, but very inefficient for all others. Each trial was run multiple times to ensure consistency and the data turned out almost identical every time. Thus there is very high confidence that the results of this project are very accurate. One of the biggest limitations of this project is the fact that the maximum number tested was less than 2^{32} . In real life cryptographic applications, numbers such as 2^{128} are used for scalar multiplication. Nonetheless, even if larger numbers were used, it is hypothesized that the relative efficiencies of the algorithms would not change. More specifically, all the algorithms would be slower, but the differences in speed would be around the same. The algorithm speeds for larger numbers also could be predicted with the best-fit lines in figures 5 and 6.

6. CONCLUSION

The results of this project have huge implications for the Internet technology industry. The algorithm created in this project runs with far greater efficiency than one of the industry's best algorithms, the Binary Double-Add Algorithm. The implementation of this algorithm into websites for e-commerce or email could mean huge speedups in performance. The increase in speed could also allow cryptographers to use larger key sizes for greater security, without having to compromise speed. Ideas for improving this algorithm include implementing a finite field in base 3 or even finding variations of this algorithm that improve certain security issues such as resistance to side-channel attacks. Another possibility for future work is implementing this algorithm with special large integer ($> 2^{32}$ bits) manipulation, parallelization [16], or programming NIST recommended elliptic curves.

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Authors

Vinay S. Iyengar is currently a high school junior at one of the top science schools in the United States, the Oregon Episcopal School (OES) in Portland, Oregon. He has wide interests in mathematics and sciences, particularly cryptography and bioinformatics. He is an accomplished pianist and has won numerous competitions in the greater Portland area. He currently plays the oboe with the Portland Youth Conservatory Orchestra of the Portland Youth Philharmonic. In addition, he is a varsity tennis player, and leads his school's Intercultural Student Association.

